

THE ROLE AND PLACE OF TRANSPORT LOGISTICS IN THE LOGISTICAL SYSTEM

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Resume The thesis deals with the logistics systems have come to be used as the art of managing material flow of products from source to consumer, that is, combining the activities of various organizations related to distribution, material support, planning and management.

Key words logistics, information, management, distribution, production, transport.

The term "logistics" comes from the Greek *logistike* – is the art of calculating, reasoning. Initially, logistics was a direction in mathematical logic. Then logistics systems found application in military affairs, in particular, as a military supply technique, the art of transportation, supply and deployment of military units. In economics, logistics systems have come to be used as the art of managing material flow of products from source to consumer, that is, combining the activities of various organizations related to distribution, material support, planning and management.

Modern logistics has a lot of definitions and is interpreted as the science of rational organization of production, transport and distribution, which integrally covers the supply of the enterprise from a system perspective, organization of industrial production, distribution and sales of finished products and as a planning process, organization and implementation of inexpensive and rational delivery of goods from their places of production to their places of consumption, control of all transportation and other operations in the logistical information management system. The mission of logistics is to meet the customer's demand for goods at the lowest cost associated with the transport-warehouse-inventory planning function. According to one definition, "Logistics is the science of planning, distribution,

control, management and optimization of material flows, service flows and related information and financial flows in a certain micro and macro, meso-economic system, supply, order, material flow management and sales and distribution are organizational management; improvement of transportation technologies, storage facilities, information support, planning and control, as well as optimization of costs for efficient operation of each of these services - to the technological direction. So, improving transportation technology is a technological aspect of logistics. Logistics costs in developed countries are significant even in comparison with the gross national product. Management experience has shown that traditional opportunities and ways to improve efficiency and management in order to optimize the flow of material and cash flows have exhausted themselves and new forms and methods are needed. Supply, order, material flow management and sales and distribution are organizational management; improvement of transportation technologies, storage facilities, information support, planning and control, as well as optimization of costs for efficient operation of each of these services - to the technological direction transport. Logistics - a section of logistics of the movement of resources to manage the physical movement of material resources in space and time into the honeycomb. Information logistics is a section of resource movement (rest) logistics devoted to information flow management in micro- and macro logical systems. Financial logistics is a section of resource movement (rest) logistics dedicated to managing financial flows in micro and macro logical systems. Service logistics is a section of resource movement (rest) logistics devoted to service flow management in micro- and macro logical systems. Transport logistics is an integral part of logistics in general. It is closely related to all its subsystems. But transport logistics also acts as an independent discipline, with its own goals and objectives. Transportation - one of the key logistics functions related to the movement of products by a vehicle using a certain technology and supply chain and consisting of logistical operations and functions, including forwarding, cargo processing, packaging, transfer of rights and ownership of cargo, risk insurance and customs. Logistical object - material and

related financial and information flows. The subject of transport logistics is the organization of the movement of goods by general transport. Logistics, as noted, is a single technique, technology, economics and planning. Accordingly, the tasks of transport logistics should include ensuring the technical and technological interoperability of the participants in the transport process, coordinating their economic interests, as well as using unified planning systems. Let's briefly describe each of these tasks. 1. Technical conjugacy in the transport complex means the consistency of the parameters of vehicles both within individual views and in an interspecific section. This consistency allows you to apply modal transportation, work with containers and cargo packages. 2. Technological interoperability implies the use of a single transportation technology, direct overloads, non-overload communication. 3. Economic conjugacy is a general methodology for studying market conditions and building a tariff system. 4. Joint planning means the development and application of uniform schedules. The general task is to create an effective system for regulating and controlling material and related flows that ensure high quality delivery of products. The main tasks are to ensure the transportation of goods; minimizing transportation costs finding optimal delivery routes; creation of logistic schemes, search and selection of carriers, forwarding agents; delivery planning participation in terms of logistics in pre-contract work and when concluding sales contracts; passing customs formalities in the country of departure, destination and in transit through third countries; ensuring a unified controlled delivery scheme for various carriers and types of transport during mixed (intermodal) transportation; consolidation (consolidation) of goods in the delivery process; storage in transit and temporary storage warehouses; approval of shipping instructions with the sender and recipient, etc. Individual tasks of transport logistics:

Principles of transport logistics: consistency; complexity; science; specificity; constructiveness; reliability; variability. The logistics function can be considered as an enlarged group of logistics activities aimed at realizing the goals of the logistical system. Among the main functions of transport logistics are the following:

determination of volumes and directions of movement of material flows; assessment of transportation requirements transportation of goods; execution of operations preceding and completing the transportation of goods, etc. The concept of logistics management stimulates a holistic approach to transportation management instead of a functional one, in which responsibility for stocks and responsibility for transport are independent functions of production and distribution, and decisions on them are often not agreed upon. Logistics management takes into account the relationships and interdependencies between the components of the inventory transfer and storage system.

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